

Papers on Social Representations

Early View

Peer Reviewed Online Journal

ISSN 1021-5573

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[<https://psr.iscte-iul.com/>]

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7982480

WORKPLACE STRESS AND EMPLOYEE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS: RESILIENCE AS A MEDIATOR

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Abstract

Purpose – This research aims to examine the influence of work stress with employee resilience on organizational commitment and the relationship between work stress and employee resilience with organizational commitment among employees in Non-Government Organizations (NGOs).

Design/methodology/approach – In the cross-section research design, the author used three questionnaire/scales to investigate the influence of work stress on employee resilience on organizational commitment among 150 NGO employees selected randomly.

Findings – The findings revealed that work stress influenced organizational commitment as well as employee resilience as a mediator. Another finding was that work stress and employee resilience in the organization did have positive relationships with organizational commitment.

Originality/value – The significance of the research consists in emphasising work stress as an important factor impacting organisational commitment and performance in organisations, wherein work stress impacts organisational commitment through the mediating variable- resilience. These findings may assist organisations in better understanding the impact of individuals' organisational commitment and managing its repercussions. It is proposed that more studies be conducted to see whether those working in NGOs have more organisational commitment than those working in other sectors.

Practical implications – Several organisations utilise the three scales to assess the link between employee work stress and organisational commitment. The information given indicated that they would not be gaining as much understanding as they would expect.

Originality/value – Work stress impacts organisational commitment via SEM analysis conducted, providing prima facie evidence to challenge the level of organisational commitment.

Keywords: Work Stress, Employee Resilience, Employee Commitment.

Introduction

Stress refers to people's physical and emotional reactions to changes, events, and situations in their lives. People are stressed in a variety of ways and for a variety of reasons. A person's reaction is determined by how he understands an event or a scenario. Individuals and organisations could be affected by stress, which could lead to situations that jeopardise their capacity to fulfil their goals. Stress, according to Robbins (2001), is a dynamic scenario in which an individual is faced with an opportunity, constraint, or demand connected to what he or she wants, and the consequence is regarded to be both unclear and critical. A mismatch between an individual's demands and pressures and their knowledge and talents causes stress. It interferes with their capacity to perform at work. This comprises not just circumstances in which workplace limitations exceed workers' ability to deal with them, but also situations in which a worker's knowledge and talents are underutilised and become a problem for them. When faced with adversity, such as work-related stress, resilient people have better coping and adapting capabilities (Hodges, Keeley, & Troyan, 2008).

Work stress is considered to be one of the antecedents of organisational commitment, but knowledge of the relationship between work stress and organisational commitment is inconclusive (Abdelmoteleb, 2019). Work-related stress is defined as a situation in which an individual's working conditions are unfavourable and he is unable to execute his duties. In addition, he became stressed as a result of repeated assigned tasks, and he was unable to obtain new employment alternatives. This stress finally caused a lack of organisational commitment. Individuals' emotional behaviour changes as a result of increased work stress, disconnecting them from the organisation's operations and daily routine activities. Employee behaviour is affected by workplace stress, as it is general work commitment. Employees who are stressed out in the workplace are less likely to participate in a variety of activities (Smollan, 2015).

Weiss (1983) categorized specific stressors as having a much more severe effect on an individual, such as role ambiguity, a lack of performance feedback, no career development programmes, and organisational structure and environment. Stress can be lessened if social support is present. Workplace stress is defined as a harmful response that individuals require in response to unneeded pressuring forces and demands placed on them at work.

The findings of Sajid, Ihsan, and Reba's study (2021) reveal that hostile work environments and executive rehearsals are common sources of work pressure.

Viljoen and Rothmann (2009) studied the link between occupational stress, ill health, and organisational commitment and discovered that organisational stress was an important contributor to ill health and low organisational commitment. The fear of losing one's employment contributes to both physical and mental ill health. Five stresses, such as work-life balance, overwork, control, job characteristics, and pay, were found to indicate low commitment to the organisation.

Smith et al. (2018) characterised work-related stress as a sensation of uneasiness, feeling that the work is uncontrollable, and work overload. As a result, work stress does not have to be all the times bad. It aids employees in resolving issues and has a positive impact on their professional lives. An individual should not continue to be stressed because it may develop into a burnout disorder.

Resilience refers to an organisation's ability to dynamically reinvent business models and strategies when circumstances change, and to shift before the need becomes urgent (Hamel & Valikangas, 2003). The ability of organisations and employees to resist and adapt to substantial challenges, or resilience, is critical to their survival and effectiveness. It is critical to consider how aspects of the workplace influence employees' ability to deal with day-to-day challenges and engage in resilient behaviours. These behaviours promote organisational performance and sustainability when assessing an individuals' resilience in relation to work life and their employee resilience. While early theoretical conceptualizations of employee resilience in organisations have described it as an adaptive behavioural capacity to gather, integrate, and utilise organisational resources (Richardson, 2002). Recent theoretical conceptualizations of employee resilience in organisations describe it as an adaptive behavioural capacity to gather, integrate, and use organisational resources (Kuntz et al., 2016, 2017). However, observable behaviours that explain how individual resilience leads to favourable organisational results are still needed. Employee resilience, as well as the behaviours that signal it, is the product of a complex interaction of personal and environmental factors. When a business encourages proactive, adaptive, and support-seeking behaviours, workers are more willing to be resilient. Employees' resilience could be seen in activities like resource identification and use, as well as learning and change-oriented behaviours.

Resilient employees not only persist in the face of adversity, but they also believe in their abilities, which leads to higher levels of employee engagement (Cooke et al., 2016; Hodliffe, 2014). A firm belief in the organisation's goals and ideals is defined as organisational commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Doan et al. (2020) proposed that the power of identification between employees and an organisation is referred to as organisational commitment. Employees that are passionate about their jobs are more concerned about their work.

Effective attachment, according to Huang, You, and Tsai (2012), is part of a happy workplace since it is built on commitment-based personal identification with the organisation's values and goals. The present study aims to see how work stress and employee resilience affect organisational commitment, as well as how employee resilience affects organisational commitment among NGO workers.

Review of Literature

Swaminathan and Rajkumar (2013) examined stress levels in different age groups, professions, and different types of occupations, work hours, and the impact of the work environment on employee stress levels based on the individual nature of employees' proneness to stress. Their findings revealed the optimum level at which employees could achieve the best results, and three circumstances that contributed to workplace stress were identified, such as 1) role overload 2) role self-distance and 3) role stagnation.

Mkumbo et al., (2014) examined the incidence of and causes of job stress among academic staff in public and private institutions in a study on work stress. They discovered that work stress is a typical occurrence in higher education institutions as a result of low job satisfaction, which is likely to influence staff efficiency. Employee identification and involvement in the organisation were described as organisational commitment (Porter et al., 1974).

Individuals who are committed to sharing ideals, like to keep their membership, and are willing to put forth work on behalf of the organisation. In their study on Sense Of Coherence (SOC), Urakawa and Yokoyam (2009) found that SOC could help Japanese manufacturing employees' mental health by reducing the consequences of occupational stress. Their findings revealed that occupational pressures had a detrimental influence on mental health. Furthermore, workplace stress was positively connected with SOC; and males in management positions had a poor mental health status, whereas female co-workers had a favourable mental health status. Finally, they discovered that SOC is an important factor in predicting men's and women's abilities to cope with occupational stress.

Treven, Treven, and Zizek (2011) found that workers who were reported to be stressed were more likely to be unsuccessful at work. The most successful stress-reduction measures were varied approaches to stress management, excellent work organisation, and good management.

Shahid et al. (2012) used six stress components to investigate work stress and employee performance in the banking sector in Faisalabad, Pakistan. They were a lack of administrative support, excessive work demand, problematic customer relations, co-workers' relationships, family and work-life balance, and the riskiness of the job that caused great stress and decreased performance.

Resilience mechanisms, according to Fisher et al. (2019), could be defined as the experiences, reactions, and behaviours that individuals use in the face of adversity, such as coping methods or emotional responses. Personal or environmental qualities that were present regardless of an individual's experience of adversity yet could buffer the negative impacts of adversity or build resilience mechanisms during unpleasant experiences were referred to as resilience-promoting factors.

When faced with a challenge, resilience refers to a person's capacity to respond successfully and suffer fewer negative repercussions. Recent research looked at how resilience would affect reactions to more common life concerns like health issues and work stress (Shatté et al., 2012).

Employee resilience is defined as the ability to manage resources efficiently, cope with high workloads, respond to and learn from mistakes and crises, and embrace change as a source of growth (Kuntz, Connell, & Näswall, 2017). Employees exhibited resilient behaviour when they used their personal and work-related resources to rapidly respond to uncertainty and change. Studies demonstrated that resilience could help people manage work-related stress (Kuntz, Näswall, & Malinen, 2016).

Swales (2002) defined organisational commitment as an employee's emotional connection, identification with and relationship with the organisation. In essence, measuring organisational commitment could be a comparison of an individual's personal values and beliefs to the organization's values and beliefs.

Organisational commitment, Mowday et al. (2000), referred to being loyal to the company as well as the company being loyal to the employee. This definition clearly understated the complexity of an individual's attitude toward and behaviour inside his employing organisation.

Allen and Meyer (1990), described Organisational commitment as an attitude that relates to individual mindsets toward the organisation. Employees who were committed to the company were more likely to complete their responsibilities thoroughly and remain with the organisation longer than those who were not.

Organisational commitment was described by Wagner and Hollenbeck (2010) as employee identification with the organisation. It signified that the employee was willing to put forth a significant amount of effort on behalf of the company and that he or she intended to stay with the company for a long period of time. Others regarded organisational commitment as an emotional reaction exhibited through employee behaviours, beliefs, and attitudes (Meyer & Allen, 1997). It would be a psychological state that showed an employee's level of commitment to a company.

Meng et al. (2017) investigated resilience as a predictor of organisational commitment and burnout, as well as the mediating effects of leader-member exchange (LMX) and team-member

exchange (TMX). According to their SEM analysis, (a) resilience predicted LMX and TMX, and (b) LMX, not TMX, partially mediated the relationships between employee resilience and organisational commitment and work burnout.

Objectives

The objectives were as follows

To assess the impact of the mediation effect of work stress on the link between work stress and employee commitment using a framework.

The following were the hypotheses:

- H1. Employee commitment will be influenced by work stress with employee resilience.
- H2. Work stress with employee resilience will mediate employee commitment.
- H3. Work stress as well as employee resilience will significantly relate to organisational commitment.

Materials and Methods

Participants

Employees of NGOs were chosen for the study using a random sample method in the cross-section study design. The participants completed these scales and they took about 20 minutes. The research comprised 150 employees from non-profit organisations, but no personal information was collected, such as names or email addresses.

Measures:

The study used three standardised tools that were previously used by other research investigators.

Tools

1. The American Institute's Work Stress Scale consists of ten items which are scored on a 5-point Likert-type scale, from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).
2. Employee Resilience Scale (Näswall et al. 2019) consists of 9 items that are rated on a 1–5-point Likert scale.
3. British Organisational Commitment Scale (Ashman, 2006) consists of 9 items that rated on a 1–5-point Likert scale.

Statistics

The data was analysed using the SPSS-Version 23 statistical software. The goal of this research was to explore if a mediation hypothesis could be proven. Descriptive and inferential statistics-regression and correlation analysis was utilised to understand the prediction and the relationship between the independent factors and the dependent variable. Process-Macro was used to explore the mediation hypothesis.

Results

Figure 1: Influence of Work Stress on Organisational Commitment through Employee Resilience

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation

Note: N=150, **p<0.01

S.No	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Work Stress	Employee Resilience	Organisational Commitment
1	Work Stress	150	2.47	0.50	1	-	-
2	Employee Resilience	150	3.68	0.59	0.55**	1	-
3	Organisational Commitment	150	3.87	0.57	0.97**	0.45**	1

The mean for work stress is 2.47 (SD=0.50), Employee resilience has a mean of 3.68 (SD=0.59), and Organisational Commitment has a mean of 3.87 (SD=0.57). Work stress positively correlates with organisational commitment (r=0.97, p<0.01) followed by Employee resilience (r=0.55, p<0.01). Employee resilience correlates with organisational commitment (r=0.45, p<0.01).

Table 2: Interpretation of mediation model

Predictors	B	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	R square	F
Outcome variable (Employee Resilience) (a path)								
Organisational Commitment	0.0017	0.0221	45.2840	0.00	0.0454	0.9580	0.9327	2050.6418
Outcome Variable (Work Stress) (b path)								
Organisational Commitment	-0.1257	0.2136	-5.2712	0.00	-0.7037	-0.5478	0.4151	52.1621
Employee Resilience	0.5156	0.2059	7.3606	0.00	0.1087	0.9225		
Total, Direct and Indirect effect								
Total effect X on Y (c path)	0.3924	0.0646	6.0738	0.00	0.2647	0.5200	0.1995	36.8910
Direct effect X on Y controlling M (c' path)	-0.1257	0.2136	-5.2712	0.00	-0.7037	-0.5478	-	-
Indirect effect (B)	0.5181	0.2010	-	-	0.1100	0.9100	-	-

Note: N=150, **p<0.01, X-Organisational Commitment, M-Employee Resilience, Y-Work Stress

From the above table, the R square was 0.9327 and the F value was 2050.6418. The p-value was significant (p<0.01) for a path. For the b path, the R square was 0.4151 and the F value was 52.1621. The p-value was significant (p<0.01) for Organisational Commitment. Similarly, for Employee resilience, the p-value was also significant (p<0.01). The total effect c path (B=0.3924, t=6.0738, p<0.01, LL=0.2647, UL=0.5200). The direct effect c' path (B=-0.1257, t=-5.2712, p<0.01, LL=-0.7037, UL=-0.5478). c' is smaller than the c path so the effect is controlled by the mediator Employee resilience and c' becomes insignificant. The indirect effect (B=0.5181, LL=0.1100, UL=0.9100). Here the direct effect and indirect effect are significant and the confidence intervals do not include a zero. Thus, the model fully mediates the relationship between organisational commitment and work stress through employee resilience.

Discussion:

Workplace stress, according to Smith et al. (2018), does not have to be all harmful. Employees' involvement in problem-solving has a positive impact on their professional lives. The current study found that work stress and employee resilience have an impact on organisational commitment. Employees in non-profit organisations with moderate levels of work stress and employee resilience are more likely to have a higher level of organisational commitment eventually in their careers.

Hamel and Valikangas (2003) supported that various factors in the workplace influence employees' ability to deal with day-to-day stressors and engage in resilient behaviours. When analysing an individual's resilience about work stress and employee adoption behaviour, these behaviours support organisational effectiveness and commitment. Further, Cooke et al. (2016) also found that workers are more willing to be resilient if their workplace is proactive, adaptive, and supportive. Employees have faith in their abilities, which leads to increased dedication.

Workplace stress was highly linked to female coworkers' sense of coherence and mental health condition. Employees demonstrate resilient behaviour when they use their personal and work-related resources to quickly respond to uncertainty and change. Kuntz, Näswall, and Malinen (2016) found that resilience can support people cope with work-related stress.

Employees that are committed to the firm are more likely to execute their tasks fully and stay with the company for a longer period (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Workplace stress has both a positive and negative impact on employee morale. The impact of organisational commitment was determined by the level of work stress and resilience. The greater the level of work stress and resilience the greater the organisational commitment, and hence the probability of overcoming organisational commitment. The regression equation clearly shows that the high the work stress the higher the perception of organisational commitment.

Employees were put under more stress when their resilience was lessened, resulting in a lack of organisational commitment. As a result, the impact of organisational dedication is magnified. It is critical to have moderate work stress because it leads to greater commitment. This is also reflected in the regression equation: the higher the resilience the more the organisational commitment. The higher the work stress and resilience also had the more the organisational commitment. Employees who are highly committed to their jobs are happier and have fewer health issues.

Conclusion:

The study's findings are that work stress and resilience are contributing elements that influence organisational commitment, particularly among NGO employees. Future studies could focus on other organisations. The variables that potentially affect employee commitment to the organisation were investigated in this study. The impact of organisational commitment on other measures such as work engagement, life satisfaction, job satisfaction, and so on could be the subject of future investigations. They can advance their careers by knowing the organisation's employee

commitment. Understanding the nature of the employee could help the company create a positive work culture that encourages employee contribution and productivity.

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